

Ethyl Acetate as a Polar Solvent. Part IV. Solubility of Substances, Formation of Solvates, and the Nature of the Solutions of Lewis Acids in Ethyl Acetate

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Solubility determinations of a large number of compounds in ethyl acetate show that those of predominantly ionic in nature are insoluble and those of predominantly covalent in nature are soluble, as is expected of a solvent with a low dielectric constant. Ethyl acetate forms a number of solvates with Lewis acids and other compounds. The constitution of the compounds has been studied by measuring conductances of their solutions and dipole moments. Organic tertiary bases do not form any solid solvates, but conductances of their solutions definitely indicate the interaction of the solvent and the solute to produce more ionic species. The structures of the solvates with Lewis acids and bases are proposed on the basis of the auto-ionisation of the solvent as $\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3\text{CO}^+ + \text{OC}_2\text{H}_5^-$.

In the earlier parts of the series¹⁻⁴, the mode of ionisation of ethyl acetate, as represented by equation (i):

was explored. A few conductometric titrations between ansolvo acids and organic tertiary bases and certain solvolytic reactions in ethyl acetate in support of the above mode of ionisation were also reported.

Nauman⁵ qualitatively determined solubilities of some of the compounds in ethyl acetate and carried out certain metathetical reactions, but he did not mention the existence of the ion pairs during the course of the reaction.

Solubility of the substances in this solvent reveals that, in general, only the covalent compounds are soluble and the ionic compounds are insoluble. This is expected of a solvent having a low dielectric constant. Solubility of the compounds has been studied quantitatively and in some cases qualitatively. The results are presented in Table II. Lewis acids dissolved in it with evolution of heat to form coloured solutions, indicating the formation of complexes and in some cases a solid complex separated. Pyridine, quinoline, picolines (α , β , and γ), dimethylaniline, and diethylaniline are all miscible with ethyl acetate and there is no detectable evolution of heat or any change in the colour of the mixture. There is, however, an increase in conductance of the resulting solutions, indicating formation of ionic species due to formation of the new compounds; but no solid solvate separates even on the addition of inert solvents like carbon tetrachloride or petroleum to the mixtures.

1. Paul and Malhotra, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1963, **321**, 56.
2. Paul *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, **321**, 70.
3. Paul *et al.*, *Res. Bull. Panjab Univ.*, 1963, 173.
4. Paul and Malhotra, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, (in press).
5. *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 313.

The tendency of Lewis acids to form adducts with organic compounds containing basic oxygen is well known. Tetrahalides of tin^{6,7}, titanium^{8,9}, tellurium, and zirconium¹⁰, trichlorides of aluminium, antimony, and iron, and sulphur trioxide form addition products with esters.

Magnesium chloride forms an unstable disolvate with ethyl acetate of composition $MgCl_2 \cdot 2CH_3CO_2Et$. Similarly anhydrous calcium chloride and bromide form disolvates $CaCl_2 \cdot 2CH_3CO_2Et$ and $CuBr_2 \cdot 2CH_3CO_2Et$, whereas the halides of higher members of the same group are completely insoluble in ethyl acetate and do not form any solvate with it. With ethyl acetate cadmium chloride and iodide form monosolvates and zinc chloride, trisolvate, $ZnCl_2 \cdot 3CH_3CO_2Et$, which loses under vacuum two molecules of the ester, affording a monosolvate. Mercuric chloride does not form any solvate with this ester. Even on addition of an inert solvent to a solution of mercuric chloride in ethyl acetate, only mercuric chloride separates. All attempts to separate solvates of organic tertiary bases with ethyl acetate have failed. The solvates isolated are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Solvate formation.

Compound.	Solvate.	Colour.	% Metal.		% Halogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
ZnCl ₂	ZnCl ₂ ·3CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	White	15.68	16.33	17.23	17.48
	ZnCl ₂ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	28.96	29.13	30.98	31.62
BiCl ₃	BiCl ₃ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	48.86	49.13	26.43	26.43
CaCl ₂	CaCl ₂ ·2CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	13.18	13.93	23.92	24.70
MgCl ₂	MgCl ₂ ·2CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	8.96	8.96	26.00	26.13
CdCl ₂	CdCl ₂ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	40.98	41.41	25.86	26.12
CdI ₂	CdI ₂ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	24.18	24.74	54.96	55.08
ZnI ₂	ZnI ₂ ·2CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	Yellow	12.86	13.19	49.84	51.26
SnCl ₂	SnCl ₂ ·2CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	32.16	32.45	18.96	19.41
PCl ₅	PCl ₅ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	White	10.08	10.45	59.16	59.86
SbCl ₃	SbCl ₃ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	..	53.21	53.81	42.21	42.65
AlCl ₃	AlCl ₃ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	Yellow	11.90	12.22	48.00	48.29
FeCl ₃	FeCl ₃ ·2CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	Reddish brown	16.88	16.54	33.62	31.48
TeCl ₄	TeCl ₄ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	Yellow	31.98	32.09	39.12	39.70
TiCl ₄	TiCl ₄ ·2(CH ₃ CO ₂ Et)	..	12.89	13.09	38.12	38.80
SbCl ₅	SbCl ₅ ·CH ₃ CO ₂ Et	Reddish brown	31.12	31.44	45.12	45.01

The constitution of these solvates and of the solutions containing Lewis acids and bases in ethyl acetate may be profitably discussed by taking into consideration the electrical properties of these solutions. The specific conductances of Lewis acids and bases and of other compounds have been determined in ethyl acetate at $27^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results are presented in Table II.

6. Rosenheim and Levy, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 3662.
7. Osipov, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1956, **26**, 322.
8. Osipov and Suckkov, *ibid.*, 1952, **22**, 1132.
9. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2773.
10. Osipov and Kletenik, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1957, **27**, 2921.

TABLE II

*Solubilities and sp. conductance of solutions of substances in ethyl acetate.*Sp. conduc. of EtOAc = 3×10^{-9} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹

Substance.	Solubility (g./100 g.).	Conc. (mole/litre).	Sp. conduc. (mho).	Heat effect.
HgCl ₂	62.80	0.02216	0.862×10^{-6}	..
HgBr ₂	28.20	0.01820	0.625×10^{-6}	..
CaCl ₂	2.60	0.02482	0.818×10^{-6}	Exothermic
CaBr ₂	1.80	0.02658	0.886×10^{-6}	..
CaI ₂	18.60	0.02186	0.586×10^{-6}	..
FeCl ₃	40.92	0.00882	0.826×10^{-5}	..
MgBr ₂	0.98	0.00212	0.248×10^{-6}	..
MgCl ₂	3.20	0.02848	0.342×10^{-5}	..
ZnCl ₂	1.60	0.01246	0.622×10^{-5}	..
SnCl ₂	12.40	0.01082	0.646×10^{-5}	..
CdCl ₂	1.60	0.03108	0.242×10^{-5}	..

N. B. Sp. conductances of Lewis acids have already been published³.

The solutions of Lewis acids in ethyl acetate are fairly conducting and the conductance of these solutions is quite significant as the individual components are non-conducting. The high conductance of these solutions indicates the formation of definite solvates and their ionic character. The nature of the complexes formed has, however, been in dispute¹¹⁻¹³. Boron trichloride forms an addition compound with ethyl acetate of composition BCl₃.CH₃.CO₂.Et. Garrard and Wheelam¹⁴ observed the formation of acetyl chloride during refluxing with BCl₃ and suggested the ions present as:

Greenwood and Martin¹⁵ have studied the conductance of the molten compound of boron trifluoride and ethyl acetate and have attributed its conductance to the following ions:

Quite recently Paul *et al.*³ have established that the ions responsible for the high conductance of these solutions of Lewis acids in ethyl acetate may be:

where M and M' are the tetravalent and trivalent metals, which have a tendency to acquire hexa- and tetra-covalency respectively. On the basis of analogy, the ionic pairs in zinc chloride and magnesium chloride solutions can be represented as:

11. Brown *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 673.12. Lappert, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 817.13. Zackrisson and Lindqvist, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 17, 69.14. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4296.15. *Ibid.*, 1953, 751; *Quart. Rev.*, 1954, 8, 1.

Similarly with cadmium chloride, it may furnish ions in solution as:

Aluminium chloride, ferric chloride, and antimony trichloride have been used as Lewis acids in acetyl chloride¹⁶ and nitrosyl chloride¹⁷ and it has been established that these metal atoms have a tendency to acquire a tetra-covalency. Here also these form solvates with ethyl acetate, which may ionise to afford ionic pairs.

The increase in conductance of ethyl acetate in presence of pyridine, quinoline, α -picoline, dimethylaniline, and diethylaniline, which do not form any solid solvate under ordinary conditions, is indeed interesting. These substances having a tertiary nitrogen are presumed to form, in solutions, solvates, which ionise to furnish cations containing quadrivalent nitrogen. Though no solvate separates, the increase in conductance can only be due to the formation of strongly polar compounds, furnishing ions to conduct current. Since these organic tertiary bases are known to form conducting solutions in other polar solvents like acetyl chloride etc. and the ions formed are well established, by analogy the ions responsible for the conductance in ethyl acetate may be assumed to be:

Though the increase in the conductance is not to the same extent as in the case of the solutions of Lewis acids in ethyl acetate, the increase is quite significant when compared with the that of the pure components. This is due to its basic nature and thus the reluctance to accept electrons from the organic tertiary bases.

Further light on the structure of the solvates has been thrown by studying their dipole moments. All the measurements were made in benzene solutions. The results have been calculated by the method proposed by Hedestrand¹⁸ and modified by LeFevre and Vine¹⁹ for dilute solutions in non-polar solvents. The results are recorded in Table III and indicate the high polarity of the complexes.

TABLE III

Lewis acid.	Compound.	Dipole moment in benzene.
AlCl_3	$\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{AlCl}_3$	5.00
SbCl_3	$\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{SbCl}_3$	4.22
FeCl_3	$\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{FeCl}_3$	5.32
SbCl_5	$\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{SbCl}_5$	5.94
TeCl_4	$\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{TeCl}_4$	5.82
SnCl_4	$2\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{SnCl}_4$	Insoluble
$^*\text{TiCl}_4$	$2\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{TiCl}_4$	6.28

*Kletenik and Oaipov²⁰ report $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} = 5.03$; $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{Et} = 6.65$.

16. Dickenson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 544.
17. Lewis and Sowerby, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1956, 75, 615.
18. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, B2, 428.
19. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1805.
20. *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1961, 31, 710.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl acetate, Lewis acids, and organic tertiary bases were purified by the methods already described¹.

To determine solubility of the various compounds, solvent was added to a well-dried ampule containing sufficient quantity of the compound; but if the reaction was exothermic, the compound was added in small amounts to the thoroughly cooled ethyl acetate contained in the ampule. The ampule was immediately sealed and shaken in a thermostat maintained at $27^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ for 24 hr. The ampule was broken and the slurry formed was filtered quickly through a sintered glass funnel in a dry atmosphere. The solubility of the substance in 100 g. of ethyl acetate was determined by estimating the metal from the known weight of the solution.

The solvates of the liquid Lewis acids, SbCl_3 and TiCl_4 , with ethyl acetate were prepared by keeping the ester in a freezing mixture and liquid Lewis acids were added from a dropping funnel with constant stirring. After keeping the mixture in an ice bath for 2 hr., the solid was separated by filtration in a dry atmosphere and washed with dry petroleum (b.p. $40-60^{\circ}$); excess of petroleum was removed by keeping under vacuum for 5 minutes and the compound was analysed.

The solvates of AlCl_3 , FeCl_3 , SbCl_3 , and TeCl_4 were prepared by mixing Lewis acids in the ice-cold ethyl acetate and allowing the mixture to stand for about 2 hr. The mixtures were then warmed and again cooled. A solid compound separating was filtered in a dry atmosphere, washed with light petroleum, kept under vacuum, and analysed.

The solvates of ZnCl_2 , ZnBr_2 , ZnI_2 , CaCl_2 , CaBr_2 , CdBr_2 , CdI_2 , MgCl_2 , PCl_3 , and MgI_2 were prepared by adding the solid compound (5 g.) to ethyl acetate (20 ml) in a sealed ampule. The reaction mixture was shaken in a thermostat at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ for about 24 hr. The solid was separated by filtration and washed with dry petroleum (b.p. $40-60^{\circ}$). Last traces of petroleum were removed by keeping under vacuum for 5 min.

Precision measuring bridge type WBR No. 108 with logarithmic amplifier of type TAV, IKC No. 034, manufactured by Wissenschaftlich Technische Werkstätten Wielheim/Oby, Germany, was used for determining conductance of the solutions. A solution of the known concentration was directly prepared in the conductivity cell of cell constant 0.34. Since the conductance of the bases in ethyl acetate was low, a specially designed cell of cell constant 0.034 was used. All measurements were made at $27^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ by placing the conductivity cell in a thermostat, regulated to that temperature.